

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

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ABSTRACT:	<p>The occurrence of public emergencies such as COVID-19 pandemic has had unprecedented challenges on the healthcare systems, shutting down economics and greatly affecting clinical research ecosystem. On 11th March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) as a Pandemic. In response, most countries including the Uganda government-imposed measures that slowed the transmission of COVID-19 during the pandemic. While the measures may have helped to disrupt the spread of the virus, they also disrupted the conduct of research activities. Across the globe, concerted efforts were made to respond to the pandemic through release of information faster than any other event in research history. However, the search for a scientifically and actionable interventions raised significant ethical complexities and challenges observed in research during the</p>

	<p>pandemic. Comparably, the lockdowns and travel restrictions had a direct impact on ethical conduct of research in Uganda. A study exploring the experiences and lessons learnt by researchers in an HIV trial in Uganda, reflected on the need to adhere to local regulations, government policies as well as the ethical principles which consequently affected the overall management of the trial during the pandemic. While some studies have documented the experiences and lessons learnt by researchers and study participants in research during COVID-19 pandemic, there is paucity of data on how the COVID-19 affected the research regulatory ecosystem in Uganda. Therefore, this research study will examine the effect of public health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic on the research regulatory systems in Uganda to identify gaps and implement targeted improvement and better preparedness for future public health emergencies.</p>
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THE EFFECT OF PUBLIC HEALTH EMERGENCIES ON THE RESEARCH REGULATORY SYSTEMS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF COVID-19 IN UGANDA

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AVAREF	African Vaccines Regulatory Forum
BMC	BioMedical Central
BU	Boston University
COVID-19	CoronaVirus Disease 2019
CTSA	Clinical and Translational Science Awards
EDCTP	European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
EUREC	European Network of Research Ethics Committees
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
FTRPs	Fast Track Review Procedures
HSP	Human Subject Protection
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
ICH-GCP	International Council for Harmonisation-Good Clinical-Practice
IDI	In-Depth Interviews
IRB	Institutional Review Board
KII	Key Informant Interviews
NARC	National HIV/AIDS Research Committee
NDA	National Drug Authority
NRA	National Regulatory Agencies
NRIMS	National Research Information Management system
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PIR	Post-Implementation Reviews
REC	Research Ethics Committee
RTR	Rapid Turnaround Review
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
UNCST	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology
UNHRO	Uganda National Health Research Organization
USA	United States of America
WHO	World Health Organization

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background

Public Health Emergencies (PHEs) are events or situations that pose significant threats to the health of communities or populations. PHE is “an occurrence or imminent threat of an illness or health condition, caused by bioterrorism, epidemic or pandemic disease, or a novel and highly fatal infectious agent or biological toxin, that poses a substantial risk of a significant number of humans [fatalities] or incidents or permanent or long-term disabilities (WHO, 2022). Nelson et al (2007) define PHEs as “any situations whose health consequences have the potential to overwhelm routine capabilities to address them due to the scale, timing or unpredictability of the situation”. They can be due to various causes and can have local, national, or international implications. Understanding and preparing for these emergencies is crucial to minimizing their impact on the health and well-being of populations.

Between 2007 and 2020, the frequency of PHEs has been increasing. From the H1N1 influenza pandemic (2009), Ebola (West African outbreak (2013–2015, outbreak in the Democratic Republic of Congo 2018–2020), poliomyelitis (2014 to present), Zika (2016), and COVID-19 (2020 to present) (Wilder-Smith & Osman, 2020). Globally, approximately 362 million people are directly affected by PHEs annually resulting from natural and human-made hazards (AMREF, 2022). While the frequency and diversity of zoonotic disease outbreaks have become major public health threats, there are many other risks that need to be addressed including bioterrorism and slow-onset risks such as antimicrobial resistance (IFRC, 2021). As such, many countries are reviewing their regulatory preparedness for prevention, mitigation, and recovery activities to respond to these events. For instance, the United States has increased investment in excess of \$5 billion to increase the country’s ability to prepare for and respond to PHEs (Nelson et al., 2007). Many low- and middle-income countries remain inadequately prepared during PHE events.

One of the thirteen core capacities identified by the International Health Regulations (IHR) for countries to effectively detect and respond to public health risks and emergencies is national “system preparedness” (WHO, 2005). During the 2009 pandemic and more recent pandemics, Ebola and COVID-19, the absence of well-functioning national regulatory systems was identified as one of the potential barriers for countries’ timely receipt and deployment of medical products (WHO, 2022) . The absence of robust research regulatory systems (policies, institutions, processes and tools to pursue and maintain good quality research) to address the specific challenges of PHEs remains a challenge. Moreover, the poor adoption of features such as regulatory provisions for reliance, a fast-tracking registration process, and an effective and adaptable pharmacovigilance system has further compounded the limited preparedness of developing countries to respond to these events. And yet, research regulatory systems play a crucial role in the context

of regulatory preparedness for PHEs. These systems are designed to oversee and manage scientific investigations, ensuring that research activities adhere to ethical standards, safety protocols, and legal requirements.

During PHE events, research becomes a vital component in understanding, controlling, and mitigating the impact of the emergency. Whereas Africa has made great strides in promoting preparedness and resilience to these threats, including the development of policies that guide regional and national emergency interventions, the region continues to experience threats of novel and re-emerging infectious diseases (AMREF, 2023). On average, the region records one hundred outbreaks per year (Talisuna et al., 2020) and there have been at least 1,910 reported incidents of disease outbreaks across Africa between 1970 and 2019 (Mbousou, et al., 2019). Specifically, the East Africa region continues to face recurrent outbreaks and disasters. In the past three years alone, the region faced outbreaks of diseases including cholera, Ebola, Marburg, measles, and Rift Valley Fever. Increased regional movement of people for trade and travel between the countries presents a risk of rapid cross-border spread of diseases and other PHEs. Uganda is highly vulnerable to PHEs due to its geographic location next to the Congo Basin epidemic hot spot, placement within multiple epidemic belts, high population growth rates, and refugee influx (Kayiwa et al., 2021).

In Uganda, like in many other countries, the regulatory framework for research is managed and maintained by Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) which has established guidelines, standards and frameworks to ensure that research is conducted responsibly and ethically. In the context of PHEs, these regulatory systems ensure that studies conducted prioritize participant safety and adhere to ethical principles. This oversight is crucial, especially when dealing with vulnerable populations or when interventions may have immediate consequences (WHO, 2020).

Through structures like Research Ethics Committees (RECs), the National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) in Uganda together with the UNCST ensure that research methodologies and interventions meet high safety and quality standards especially when testing new drugs, vaccines, or medical interventions in the context of a PHE. The Ministry of Health (MoH) established the National Public Health Emergency Operation Centre (PHEOC) to enhance its capacity to respond to disease outbreaks and other PHEs. Uganda has also implemented several interventions that have contributed to prevention, early detection, and effective response to PHEs (Ario et al., 2023).

Whereas responding to PHEs requires decision-making in a context that is different from “business as usual”, many of these countries lack adequate preparedness in terms of plans and tools for timely response.

And yet, these unique events influence all phases of the research regulatory value chain. Specifically, PHEs can bring about confusion and unnecessary delays if the roles of the different actors are ill-defined; or the powers and controls (such as the ability to make or exercise emergency powers, impose quarantines, etc.) are vague. The absence of robust research regulatory systems during a PHE can have adverse effects since functional regulatory systems are particularly crucial to achieving equitable access to quality-assured and safe medical products during such events. This is because PHEs could give rise to the use of unregistered, investigational, or candidate medical products with a minimum set of quality, safety, and efficacy data. During the 2009 pandemic and more recent pandemics, Ebola and COVID-19, a lack of well-functioning national systems for regulatory approval was identified as one of the potential barriers to countries' timely receipt and deployment of medical products (WHO, 2021).

The control of emergencies is a core function of Public Health systems. Certainly, natural or human made effects or emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases such as COVID-19, Ebola, Marburg, severe respiratory diseases, and hemorrhagic fevers among others constitute a public health risk that requires an urgent, coordinated, and well-organized response from governments and healthcare systems (Aristei et al., 2022). Notably, the COVID-19 pandemic had the worst effects that claimed human lives and left serious challenges in the functioning of the research regulatory system (Omary et al., 2020).

The global spread of SARS-CoV-2 and the thousands of deaths caused by coronavirus (COVID-19) led the World Health Organization to declare a pandemic on 12 March 2020. The world lost human lives, economic repercussions, and increased poverty during the COVID-19 pandemic (Ciotti et al., 2020). The subsequent lockdowns and restrictions directly impacted the research quality assurance system across the world as compliance with ethics guidelines for research became even more critical. By March 2021, more than 4,900 studies and trials had been registered worldwide (Pundi et al., 2020). The increase in the number of emerging COVID-19 research projects resulted in an overwhelming number of research project submissions to ethics and scientific committees and research regulatory bodies. Key aspects of the review of studies, like rigorousness, responsiveness, and timeliness were put to the test.

The pandemic forced many research regulatory agencies across the world to develop emergency regulatory responses in a context where the clinical picture of the virus had not been fully understood and with the lack of robust evidence based on the effectiveness of containment measures (Maciel, 2021). Funders rapidly implemented research calls, expedited review processes, hurriedly constructed methodologies, compressed research timelines, and rushed through publications. From regulatory management tools, regulatory impact assessments, stakeholder engagement and ex-post evaluation, these emergency procedures aimed to ensure robust regulatory oversight in research regulation.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, at least a quarter of the world's regulatory agencies issued COVID-19 guidance documents, expediting standard review, and approval processes (Wegner & Science, 2021). European countries put in place accelerated procedures for the evaluation and authorization of clinical trials related to the management of the pandemic covering also the Research Ethics Committee (REC) review process (Tusino & Furfaro, 2022). The European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC) issued a statement that stressed that the administrative processes for reviewing research protocols during the COVID-19 pandemic must be accelerated and simplified if these protocols are related to the treatment, prevention or diagnosis of infections caused by SARS-CoV-2. In the Netherlands, implementation of so-called 'fast-track-review-procedures' (FTRPs) enabled a swift start of urgent and relevant research (Ijkema et al., 2021). In Latin America, 53% of the countries issued legal or guidance documents in order to streamline ethics review and oversight of research in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (Palmero et al., 2021). In Pakistan, the anticipated increase in research reviews in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic led to the introduction of a national rapid turnaround review (RTR) system, catering specifically to the public health emergency (Shekhani et al., 2021).

Across Africa, regulatory agencies and Research Ethics Committees (RECs) agreed to combine their expertise to expedite clinical trial review and approvals for new multinational preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic interventions to the COVID-19 pandemic (Bekker & Mizrahi, 2020) for example Remdesivir, innovative test kits and assays. By April 2020, member states of the African Vaccines Regulatory Forum (AVAREF) agreed to adopt measures, like the use of an online platform for joint reviews of clinical trial applications for preventive, diagnostic and therapeutic interventions related to the COVID-19 pandemic. Specific countries across Africa, reviewed their guidelines or developed new ones to respond to the research ethics issues around COVID-19 research. For instance, in Egypt, new guidelines required the RECs to come up with "out-of-the box" solutions to maintain an effective, accelerated review while at the same time practicing the ethical principles required. These included on-line conferencing, digital signatures, and the increased frequency of meetings to every other day, then every week or twice a week instead of the previous monthly schedule.

The COVID-19 pandemic in Uganda was part of the ongoing worldwide crisis. The Uganda UNCST as part of its mechanism to adapt the global regulatory climate where conduct of research was on-going, developed the National Guidelines for Conduct of Research during Coronavirus Disease, 2020 to streamline conduct of research during the COVID-19 pandemic. The RECs have established systems to fast track the development and testing of effective and safe means (drugs, vaccines, tests) for the treatment, prevention, and diagnosis of COVID-19 infections. Inadvertently, the pandemic had major implications on the

operational outlook of RECs and in the way they undertake their routine activities. The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in an overwhelming increase in research studies submitted to research ethics committees (RECs) which presented several ethical challenges. However, no empirical work has been undertaken to establish the effects of COVID-19 on Uganda's Research Regulatory System, and particularly on the operations of the RECs in Uganda.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The occurrence of public emergencies such as COVID-19 pandemic has had unprecedented challenges on the healthcare systems, shutting down economics and greatly affecting clinical research ecosystem.

On 11th March 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) as a Pandemic (WHO, 2020). In response, most countries including the Uganda government-imposed measures that slowed the transmission of COVID-19 during the pandemic (MoH, 2020). While the measures may have helped to disrupt the spread of the virus, they also disrupted the conduct of research activities.

Across the globe, concerted efforts were made to respond to the pandemic through release of information faster than any other event in research history (Hashem *et al.*, 2020), however, the search for a scientifically and actionable interventions raised significant ethical complexities and challenges observed in research during the pandemic, Dothu (2020) & Marzouk *et al.* (2021).

Comparably, the lockdowns and travel restrictions had a direct impact on ethical conduct of research in Uganda. A study exploring the experiences and lessons learnt by researchers in an HIV trial in Uganda, reflected on the need to adhere to local regulations, government policies as well as the ethical principles which consequently affected the overall management of the trial during the pandemic (Mwanguzi *et al.*, 2021).

While some studies have documented the experiences and lessons learnt by researchers and study participants in research during COVID-19 pandemic, there is paucity of data on how the COVID-19 affected the research regulatory ecosystem in Uganda.

Therefore, this research study will examine the effect of public health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic on the research regulatory systems in Uganda to identify gaps and implement targeted improvement and better preparedness for future public health emergencies.

Overall Objective

The study seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda to identify gaps, implement targeted improvement and better preparedness for future public health emergencies.

1.4 Specific Objectives

1. To examine how COVID-19 facilitated or constrained research regulation in Uganda
2. To examine the effectiveness of Uganda research policies and guidelines during the COVID-19 pandemic.
3. To describe the coping strategies of researchers, NRAs and RECs amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Questions

- a) What were the facilitators and barriers to the research conduct during the COVID-19 pandemic March 2020- March 2023?
- b) What was the impact of the COVID-19 on the research regulatory processes in Uganda?
- c) How did the COVID-19 pandemic affect the research policies in Uganda?
- d) What were coping strategies undertaken by the researchers, NRAs and RECs in the conduct of research during the COVID-19 pandemic March 2020-March 2023?

1.5 Justification of the Study

Public Health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic necessitate rapid decision-making to address emerging public health or safety concerns (Raimi *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, regulatory systems need to adapt and expedite research processes to inform policy and management options during public health epidemics and emergencies (Mullard, 2020).

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on regulatory oversight cannot be overemphasized. A study done by Marzouk *et al.* (2021) indicated that the regulation gaps in research were worsened by the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa. These findings were further supported by London *et al.* (2020) and Theresa-Burgess *et al.* (2023), where significant ethical complexities and challenges were identified. Consequently, it's imperative to understand the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on the regulatory landscape in Uganda.

Therefore, assessing the effect of public health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic on the research regulatory systems in Uganda will help identify gaps to inform the development of specific guidelines for emergency research, and ensure the protection of participants' rights and welfare.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The study will take place in Gulu, Mbale, Mbarara, Bushenyi and Kampala districts. The study will consider regular operations of the National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) and accredited Research Ethics Committees during the COVID-19 pandemic (March 2020 to March 2023). COVID-19 disease as one of the PHEs led to world's regulatory agencies issuance of COVID-19 guidance documents, change of standard review, and approval processes and thus is a key point of study on the regulatory systems in Uganda.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Effects of Public Health (PH) Emergencies on Research Regulatory System

According to Zhao & Wu (2022), a public health emergency is defined as an international spread of an event that is likely to result in a disease that poses a public health risk to the world. The emergencies could be major epidemics including infectious diseases, mass illnesses caused by mysterious and unfamiliar origins, major food poisoning, or occupational hazards, as well as other events that occur unexpectedly and can cause serious damage to public health (Abeysinghe & Leopold, 2023). Such events are coordinated internationally as a response to prevention and management through research that ensures the quality and safety of the interventions. For example, during the COVID-19 and Ebola epidemics, governments and health organizations around the world collaborated to share information, conduct research, and develop vaccines and treatments. This international coordination helped prevent the further spread of the viruses and mitigating the impact on public health globally. Additionally, these efforts led to the establishment of guidelines for testing, contact tracing, and quarantine measures to manage the disease effectively.

Research on public health emergencies has expanded in terms of frequency, methodological, and disciplinary scope. Public health calamities are at most times concealed in everyday life and tend to break out during undefined time and space situations (Saxena *et al.*, 2019). When the emergencies break out, they are hazardous and can cause serious social and health harm. As the emergencies occur, they create a great impact on the prevention, control, and emergency response systems worldwide, including the research regulatory systems (Lowe *et al.*, 2022). However, there are instances where research on public health emergencies may not have expanded as expected due to a lack of expertise, lack of policies, and access to specialized knowledge. Consequently, such areas struggled to adequately prepare for and respond to public health emergencies, exacerbating the social and health harm caused by such crises.

According to Pakenham *et al.* (2017), most of the public health emergency studies are characterized by their urgency of carrying out data collection as immediately as the crisis happens, with the interest of obtaining baseline data before it is lost or altered. However, it is noted that fulfilling the research regulatory requirements needs careful methodical actions to conduct clinical research during a public health emergency is a great trial, with difficult operational challenges, despite the fact that it is an area of need (Lowe *et al.*, 2022). For example, the 2014-2016 Ebola outbreak in West Africa highlighted the importance of data gathering during public health emergencies. However, logistical constraints, funding issues, and political unrest hindered research projects and clinical research.

Similarly, the research regulatory bodies across the world have experienced the most urgent challenge of having a rapid review of protocols submitted by investigators during the emergency period, which have been designed to learn more about or intervene in an emergency crisis (Yeoh & Shah, 2021). This happens because of the urgent need for the medical and public health communities to get more evidence for drafting informed decisions regarding improving outcomes for patients affected by the crisis event (Falb *et al.*, 2020). Pharmaceutical companies rush through drug approvals during crises, potentially causing side effects or ineffective treatments, despite the urgent review process.

The regulatory committees tend to experience much pressure to carry out the review process quickly so that studies can get underway to address the emergency crisis at hand; yet this is supposed to be done without any relaxations of the ethical review standards (Ford *et al.*, 2021). This kind of pressure not only comes from investigators who need approval to secure funding from the sponsors of their studies, but also from many other stakeholders including world leaders, the community, the media, and professional organizations (Tamariz *et al.*, 2021). Besides the external pressure and excessive number of studies, there are challenges experienced by the research regulatory bodies in regards to the application of the Belmont principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice (Tamariz *et al.*, 2021).

During public health emergency settings, research regulatory systems encounter ethical concerns among professionals and scholars in health and humanitarian organizations, especially when it comes to debates on the lack of consensus around key ethical principles like equity, risk, beneficence and vulnerability (Archard *et al.*, 2020). Different researchers have noted differing perspectives and tensions on ethics that are based on the more social scientific and biomedical areas. During emergency settings, similar debates as above are usually magnified, especially when it comes to health research, given the nature of vulnerabilities and sensitivities related to the health research (Abeyinghe & Leppold, 2023). For example, although research regulatory systems protect certain groups like prisoners, women, children among others, they have no clear strategies on how to offer protection to the potentially vulnerable research participants who are survivors of the PH emergency event (Packenham *et al.*, 2017).

In situations where the occurrence of the PH emergency involves lockdowns and limited movements, like for the case of the COVID-19 crisis in 2020, most or all the research regulatory institutions in many regions in the world had to shut down their onsite activities, and the staff resorted to working from their homes (Ford *et al.*, 2021). This limited the workflow efficiency of these regulatory bodies, amidst the increased volumes of work and research protocols received for approval (Aarons, 2018). This limitation becomes even greater among the research regulatory bodies that have no mature electronic or web-based research submission systems; hence they get limited to work online.

Similarly, the research studies that involve human participants escalated during the COVID-19 pandemic, and this caused serious challenges to RECs all over the world to get familiarized with meeting their demands and at the same time achieve high standards of review (Sheehy et al., 2021). According to the Pan American Health Organization (2021), all research projects are required to be reviewed and approved by the RECs before their implementation, as this guarantees their social and scientific values, ethical conduct, respect for participants' rights, security, and well-being. It is the REC's responsibility to conduct ethical reviews rapidly and approve research protocols that meet ethical standards after a rigorous analysis (Pan American Health Organization, 2021). However, this process was affected by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in unprecedented research work worldwide. For this reason, the regulation of research remained essential to ensure the safety, dignity and well-being of research participants; similarly, the RECs worldwide have experienced vast new, and composite, ethical challenges (Sheehy *et al.*, 2021). Ever since the new pandemic of COVID-19 invaded the globe, researchers began research projects to comprehend the novel virus, including its epidemiology and pathogenicity, and then discover best approaches of prevention and control (Marzouk et al., 2021). Worldwide, the "Clinicaltrials.gov" has registered a total of over 4,900 studies and trials since COVID-19 pandemic started in 2019 (Marzouk *et al.*, 2021). However, the rising number of emerging studies created an overwhelming number of research project submissions to RECs, with ethical challenges on the rise (Marzouk et al., 2021).

2.2 Research Regulatory System Operations

Research regulatory agencies oversee and ensure compliance with ethical, safety, and legal standards in various research activities. They put in place guidelines necessary for conducting research that involves human subjects, animals, or certain substances (International Compilation Research Standards, 2021). These agencies play a crucial role in safeguarding participants, promoting scientific integrity, and maintaining public trust in research outcomes. Examples include the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) and IRBs (Institutional Review Boards) (Hinterleitner & Knill, 2023).

The operation of research regulatory systems involves several key components that collectively contribute to a regulatory system that ensures the ethical conduct, safety, and quality of research activities (Ministry of Health - Nigeria, 2007). For example, they develop and update guidelines that outline ethical and safety standards for different types of research, ensuring compliance with legal and ethical principles (Ministry of Health - Nigeria, 2007). Also, they are responsible for reviewing researchers' study protocols that are submitted to be reviewed, which includes information on study design, participant recruitment, informed consent, and safety measures. Regulatory agencies, often through research ethics committees (RECs) or Institutional Review Boards (IRBs), assess the ethical aspects of research to ensure that studies respect the rights and well-being of participants (Hinterleitner & Knill, 2023). Researchers need approval from

regulatory bodies before initiating a study. This approval signifies that the research aligns with established standards and is ethically sound. Regulatory agencies do monitor ongoing studies to ensure continued compliance. Audits are conducted to verify that researchers adhere to approved protocols.

Researchers are typically required to report adverse events, protocol deviations, and other relevant information during the study. This transparency helps maintain the safety and integrity of the research (Cody, 2020). In fields such as pharmaceuticals, regulatory agencies continue to monitor products after they enter the market to identify and address any unforeseen issues or risks. Regulatory agencies have the authority to enforce compliance through penalties, sanctions, or, in extreme cases, halting ongoing research if significant violations are identified (Ganguli Mitra & Sethi, 2016). They also communicate important information about research findings, safety concerns, and regulatory updates to the public, fostering transparency and trust.

International guidelines stipulate that research that involves human participants requires an independent ethics committee review (Council for International & Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS), 2016). As ingrained from the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Belmont Report, the quest for research review and approval is required because it ensures that adequate measures are put in place to safeguard and protect research participants (World Medical Association (WMA), 2013).

As a result of the increase in the number of research studies done in many low- and middle-income countries, most of which involve human participants, led to an increase in the number of Research Ethics Committees (RECs) established in many countries (Silverman et al., 2015). The committees are rooted in institutions including ministries of health, universities, research institutions, and non-governmental organizations. The RECs reviews are done in accordance with the International Council for Harmonisation-Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP) harmonized standard guidelines (ICH-GCP, 1996).

The role of the Research Ethics Committees (RECs) in the reviews is to determine whether the risk of the proposed study to potential participants is minimized and/or reasonable in relation to the relevance of the expected knowledge and outcomes of the study (Kass et al., 2007). The committee approves, criticizes, and monitors all research activities within its competence and requires changes while considering the proposed research's institutional, legal, scientific, and social implications (Silaigwana & Wassenaar, 2019). To carry its mandate, each committee must have at least two independent reviewers, one of which is not an institution's employee or affiliate and the other not a scientist. The committee usually partners with experts/consultants with the aim of obtaining advice in their areas of expertise on a regular basis during protocol reviews; though, it must work independently to ensure that any potential conflict of interests is not a real conflict (Sleem et al., 2010).

The RECs have operational guideline documents that provide guidance on the protection of human participants. Such documents include conflict of interest and research misconduct policies as well as research protocol application manuals or guidelines to aid their prospective clients (Orimadegun, 2021). The RECs are designed mainly to provide third-party review so as to reduce conflicts of interest; to protect the welfare of research participants through attention to risks, benefits, and informed consent; and to avoid exploitation of vulnerable individuals and populations (Mokgatla-moipolai & Ijsselmuiden, 2012). The RECs operate based on the three foundational ethical principles, that is respect for persons, beneficence, and justice.

Furthermore, it was noted that during the COVID-19 crisis, most RECs in different countries across the world were affected in their operations, where the monitoring and approval of studies was mainly affected by limited human resources and financial resources, limited training of members, the lack of national regulations, lack of adequate funding, as well as lack of gold standards to be followed internationally (Eyelade et al., 2012; Owusu et al., 2022).

In Uganda, according to the Uganda National Council for science and Technology (UNCST), out of the 24 accredited RECs in the country, most of them have mostly been reviewing observational studies (Nabukenya *et al.*, 2023). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the observational studies reviewed by the RECs make up 45%, while clinical trials make up 19%, and the rest of the other types of research account for only 36% (Ainembabazi et al., 2021). However, challenges similar to other low- and middle-income countries related to new emerging information and complex designs emerged in Uganda. The challenges occurred whenever the RECs were presented with protocols which stretch their expertise, for example when the members of the RECs had inadequate competences to review the research protocol(s); and this greatly affected the safety, rights and welfare of research participants (Ainembabazi et al., 2021).

2.4 Challenges for Regulation of Research during Public Health Emergencies

The World Health Organization (WHO) abridged the key universal ethical standards aimed at ensuring ethical research during the PHEs. These standards were meant to be adhered to by researchers, review bodies, funders, publishers, and manufacturers during the pandemic (Almeharish *et al.*, 2020). Ethical review during the PHEs is a crucial aspect required in ensuring the safety, dignity, and well-being of research participants (Sheehy *et al.*, 2021). Despite this, the RECs faced new, and often complex, ethical considerations and logistical challenges that exerted great pressure to conduct timely and rigorous ethical reviews (Sheehy *et al.*, 2021).

Public health emergencies often demand swift research initiatives. Regulatory agencies must balance the urgency of the situation with the need to uphold ethical standards, ensuring that research is conducted safely

and responsibly. Whereas, during emergencies, there may be pressure to expedite research without a thorough ethical review (Sethi, 2018). Balancing the urgency of public health needs with ethical considerations poses a challenge for regulatory bodies (Ma et al., 2020). On the other side, the urgency to collect and share data quickly can heighten concerns about data security and privacy (Faust et al., 2021). Regulatory agencies must ensure that data handling complies with established standards, even in crises.

Public health emergencies may strain the resources of regulatory agencies. Limited staff, funding, and infrastructure can hinder their ability to effectively review and oversee a surge in research activities. Despite the above, international collaboration becomes crucial during pandemics (World Health organization, 2018). Coordinating regulatory efforts across borders, aligning standards, and facilitating data sharing require effective communication and collaboration among regulatory agencies globally (Sethi, 2018). More still, public health emergencies are dynamic, with evolving challenges and uncertainties. Regulatory agencies must adapt their processes and guidelines in real-time to address new developments and emerging threats (Pan American Health Organization, 2022).

During PH emergencies, involving and communicating with affected communities becomes paramount. Regulatory agencies need effective strategies to engage communities, address concerns, and ensure informed consent, considering the unique challenges posed by the crisis (Ma et al., 2020). Balancing the need for accelerated access to treatments or vaccines with the requirement for sufficient evidence of safety and efficacy poses a challenge. Regulatory agencies may need to issue emergency use authorizations judiciously (Faust et al., 2021). Public health emergencies also often give rise to misinformation. Regulatory agencies must actively counter misinformation, ensuring that accurate information about research, treatments, and preventive measures reaches the public (World Health organization, 2018).

The use of technologies that included use of digital technologies, powered by mobile apps, artificial intelligence, among others also generated concerns and issues around privacy, and individual rights (Almeharish *et al.*, 2020). Potential subjects were contacted by email or phone to determine interest and eligibility. There was suspension of recruitment activities that involved face-to-face interactions with human subjects; and the virtual means were adopted instead, that involved use of phone calls, BioMedical (BMC) Zoom, Boston University (BU) Zoom Meetings for Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA), and BU Teams among others (organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2020).

According to Palmero *et al.* (2021), various countries worldwide, including Africa, have been actively participating in the advancement of COVID-19 vaccines and treatments, regardless of their limited research capacity and scarce resources. Fegert *et al.* (2020) pointed out that the COVID-19 pandemic caused an

overwhelming increase in research projects submitted to research ethics committees (RECs) for review and approval, which has led to many ethical challenges. These among others included a new accelerated mode of review, online meetings, balance of risks and benefits, measures to mitigate risks, co-enrolment in different studies, protection of a vulnerable COVID-19 population, accelerated decisions, online research, how to handle informed consent during the pandemic, and justification of placebo arm among others (Fegert *et al.*, 2020; Marzouk *et al.*, 2021). In addition, the ethics review and oversight of research remained an important aspect that ensured the social value, trusted quality and transparency of knowledge gathered, as well as protection of participants (Almeharish *et al.*, 2020).

According to Lynch *et al.* (2022), research is so important in combatting COVID-19, though ethical regulations for Human Subjects Protection (HSP) positioned a challenge during pandemic. Compliance challenges associated with the RECs were identified, some linked to review and approval, informed consent, emergency research, and research involving incarcerated people (Lynch *et al.*, 2022). Whereas, Singh *et al.* (2020) identified challenges that happened during COVID-19-related legal restrictions or logistical, staffing or operational concerns, the other major research processes which were not related to COVID-19 were significantly deferred worldwide and this implied that the welfare of many participants was at risk.

As noticed by Taylor *et al.* (2021), most research activities involving in-person interactions with subjects were either delayed or stopped during the past COVID-19 pandemic, this aimed at protecting the research subjects and staff. In the same regard, during the pandemic, on-campus research was also suspended (Taylor *et al.*, 2021).

While according to Ford *et al.* (2021), in many countries like the USA, the most common and urgent challenge was rapidly reviewing protocols submitted by investigators/ researchers that were drafted focusing on learning more about COVID-19. It was noticed that many RECs strategized plans to review these received protocols related to the COVID-19 pandemic as more rapidly as possible (Ford *et al.*, 2021). From a study done online that surveyed among the REC Directors at Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) institutions, the findings highlighted that 66% of the COVID-19 protocols were reviewed across all their committees, while only 22% of them allotted the protocols to only one committee, and 10% of them created new other committees to handle and review the COVID-19 protocols (Ford *et al.*, 2021); all the strategies were done to reduce the backlogs of unreviewed protocols and maximize turn around time for approvals.

Most of the research regulatory systems experienced significant increases in modifications or amendments to the research protocols, with the aim of adding COVID-19 related data collections processes (Loucks *et*

al., 2021). This was because in most or all the protocols, COVID-19 related data was not originally considered, and then changes to the protocols was necessary so as to gather data during the unique, transient period of time during the pandemic (Sisk & Dubois, 2020). All strategies caused temporary delays in RECs operations, with longer estimated turnaround time.

2.5 Opportunities and Coping Strategies During Public Health Emergencies

During public health emergencies, research regulatory bodies got opportunities that significantly contributed to understanding, mitigating, and managing crises (Faust et al., 2021). They explored new treatment methods, assessed the efficacy of existing interventions, studied transmission dynamics, and developed strategies for outbreak control. Additionally, research during these times led to advancements in diagnostic tools, vaccines, and public health policies, enhancing our preparedness for future emergencies (Pan American Health Organization, 2022).

Furthermore, the research regulatory bodies during PHEs diverted to implementing streamlined review procedures to accelerate the approval of research protocols related to public health emergencies (Guha-Sapir & Scales, 2020). This has helped in initiating studies promptly without compromising ethical considerations. Whereas, adapting regulations to the evolving nature of public health emergencies has permitted regulatory bodies to address unique challenges (Ganguli Mitra & Sethi, 2016). This flexibility has always enabled researchers to modify protocols as needed while maintaining compliance with ethical standards. Additionally, while adapting regulations to public health emergencies can address unique challenges, it may also create inconsistencies and confusion. Different regulatory bodies may interpret and implement these adaptations differently, leading to inconsistencies in the approval process.

As a result of public health emergencies, there is improvement in the development of communication channels by the research regulatory bodies, that facilitate quick and transparent information exchange., accompanied by regular updates, guidelines, and feedback that help researchers to understand evolving regulatory expectations and requirements (Guha-Sapir & Scales, 2020). Collaborative efforts are also achieved among regulatory bodies, research institutions, and other stakeholders that foster a coordinated approach, hence ensuring efficient resource allocation, but also minimizing duplication of efforts and facilitating a cohesive response to public health emergencies.

Emphasizing ethical principles remains crucial during public health emergencies (National Commission Science Technology and Innovation, 2020). The research regulatory bodies usually tend to prioritize the protection of research participants, which ensures that studies which are conducted during emergencies do adhere to ethical standards, such as informed consent and respect for autonomy (Smits et al., 2023). Also,

given the urgency of public health emergencies, regulatory bodies carefully assess the risks and benefits of research interventions, since balancing the need for rapid action with safety considerations is paramount in decision-making.

There is also continuous real-time monitoring of ongoing research during public health emergencies, which helps the research regulatory bodies to identify and address emerging issues promptly. This proactive approach ensures that studies remain in compliance with established protocols and regulatory standards (El-Jardali, 2023). There is also improved data sharing and transparency resulting from public health emergencies, which fosters collaboration and enables the scientific community to collectively address public health challenges. Hence regulatory bodies play a role in promoting responsible and secure data sharing practices.

Allocating resources strategically is essential during public health emergencies. The research regulatory bodies work to prioritize and support research efforts that have the greatest potential impact on understanding and mitigating emergencies (Ganguli Mitra & Sethi, 2016). After the crisis dwindles, the regulatory bodies usually conduct post-emergency evaluations that assess the effectiveness of their response strategies, which include identifying lessons learned and areas for improvement in preparation for future emergencies (Burkle, 2019). By employing these strategies, regulatory bodies aim to balance the need for urgency with ethical and safety considerations, ensuring that research conducted during public health emergencies contributes meaningfully to addressing the crisis (EU CDPC, 2018).

As a result of the PHEs especially the COVID-19 pandemic, the REC review meetings went virtual, and this led to increased participation of the REC attendance during the virtual meetings. Similarly, there were more virtual support hours to researchers, investigators, and their teams (WHO, 2020). The past pandemic also led to creation of new other committees to handle and review the COVID-19 protocols as well as conduct the research regulation processes as quickly as possible (Ford et al., 2021). This was because of the long turnaround time of protocol reviews by the RECs worldwide, and this was due to the pandemic crisis. For example, BMC set up a COVID-19 research scientific review committee, to review and prioritize proposals for COVID-19 research at BMC.

According to Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), the effect of the pandemic also resulted into development of coping strategies among which included the use of digital technologies, powered by mobile apps, artificial intelligence, and big data, provide potential opportunities to researchers and investigators to reach out to their study subjects as well as effectively conduct the studies amidst the pandemic period (OECD, 2020). According to Bolislis et al. (2021), open and well streamlined communication that involved the use of virtual communication platforms and online updates through the

pandemic proved useful in reaching out to the different stakeholders as well as improving the quality of regulatory systems provided.

The COVID-19 crisis has as well improved collaboration both across and between the different research regulation systems and with governments as well (Bolislis et al., 2021). Many government-led partnerships and global consortia were set up to work together with the RECs to ensure that the human subjects are appropriately protected against harm caused by the research studies amidst the COVID-19 pandemic (Jones et al., 2020). The collaborations aimed at bringing together efforts to build scientific knowledge and to pool resources to create solutions to the pandemic while the subjects are protected (Sheehy, 2021). The research regulatory systems worldwide obtained vast funding from different donors with an interest in conducting research while controlling the spread of COVID-19. The pandemic as well led to increased strengthening of protection of human subjects. However, a counterexample to this could be seen in the rushed development and distribution of COVID-19 vaccines. Although the research regulatory systems received significant funding, the fast-tracked approval process raised concerns about potential long-term effects and insufficient testing on certain populations. Additionally, there were instances where vaccine trials were conducted in countries with limited healthcare infrastructure, potentially exposing vulnerable subjects to harm without adequate protection.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Approach

The study will apply a qualitative research approach. To address the objectives of the study, a qualitative interview will be adopted to describe the effects of Public Health Emergencies (PHEs) on the RECs, researchers, and the research regulatory agencies in Uganda. Data will be collected using in-depth, focus groups and key informant guides. The qualitative approach will involve a deep probe and application of subjectivity. As pointed out by Kothari (2004) qualitative approach aims to gather an in-depth understanding of human behavior and the reasons that govern such behavior. Therefore, the study will generate in-depth, multi-faceted understanding of the complex situations that affected the RECs operations and research regulatory systems during public health emergencies in Uganda.

3.2 Research Design

The study will apply a descriptive design. The design will allow a clear description of the specific experiences faced by the regulatory agencies, researchers and RECs during the PHEs (Magilvy & Thomas, 2009). The summary of events that happened during the PHEs such as COVID-19, and Ebola will be documented and described. Hunter et al. (2019) emphasized that description of the experiences offers a detailed account of its consequences and creates a picture of what happened from the perceptions and perspectives of the research participants. Therefore, meaningful experiences, challenges and coping strategies the study participants will be described and shared with the stakeholders to generate measures for the preparedness of the research regulation system in Uganda to the future PHEs.

3.3 Study Setting

The study will be conducted in Seven districts in Uganda including Gulu, Mbale, Mbarara, Bushenyi, Wakiso, Mukono and Kampala. The study participants will be withdrawn among the accredited RECs and NRAs across these districts in Uganda. The partners in the regulatory system in Uganda include the researchers, the RECs, the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST), National Drug Authority (NDA), and Uganda National Health Research Organization (UNHRO). The list of RECs that is indicated in table 1 below will generated for inclusion in the study.

The roles of the respective stakeholders in the research process includes the researchers who prepares the protocol for review by the RECs, the RECs review for scientific and ethical compliance with the goal of protecting the rights and welfare of the research participants. The UNCST carries out quality assurance checks, register and issues research permit in collaboration with UNHRO and office of the president. The

NDA reviews research applications for safety, efficacy, quality, handling and use of drugs and issues trial certificates to the researchers.

Table 1: List of Accredited RECs for Inclusion in the Study

RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEES	HOST INSTITUTIONS	
Uganda Virus Research Institute (UVRI-REC)	Research-Based RECs	
Joint Clinical Research Centre (JCRC-REC)		
National HIV/AIDS Research Committee (NARC-REC)		
Vector Control Division Research Ethics Committee (VCD - REC)		
The AIDS Support Organization (TASO - REC)	Non-Government Organization-Based RECs	
Mildmay Uganda Research & Ethics Committee (MUREC)		
Hospice Africa Uganda Research Ethics Committee (HAUREC)		
Makerere School of Medicine Research Ethics Committee (SOM - REC)	Education Institution-Based RECs	
Makerere School of Biomedical Sciences Research Ethics Committee (SBS-REC)		
Makerere School of Health Sciences REC		
Clarke International University Research Ethics Committee (CIU-REC)		
Mbarara University of Science and Technology (MUST-REC)		
Gulu University Research Ethics Committee (GUREC)		
Makerere School of Medicine Research Ethics Committee (SOM - REC)		
Makerere School of Biomedical Sciences Research Ethics Committee (SBS - REC)		
Makerere School of Health Sciences REC		
Clarke International University Research Ethics Committee (CIU - REC)		
Kampala International University Research Ethics Committee (KIU - REC)		
Uganda Christian University Research Ethics Committee (UCI - REC)		
Bishop Stuart University Mbarara Research Ethics Committee		
Mengo Hospital Research Ethics Committee (MH -REC)		Hospital-Based RECs
Mulago Hospital Research & Ethics Committee (MHREC)		
Uganda Cancer Institute Research Ethics Committee (UCI -REC)		
Uganda National Health Laboratory Services Research Ethics Committee		
CURE Uganda Research Ethics Committee (CUREC)		
Mbale Regional Referral Hospital Research Ethics Committee (MRRH -REC)		
Lacor Hospital Research Ethics Committee (LHREC)		
St Francis Hospital Nsambya REC		
Uganda Heart Institute Research Ethics Committee (UHI-REC)		

3.4 Study Population

The study will be conducted among the REC Chairpersons, REC administrators, and the REC members of all the UNCST registered RECs by March 2023. The National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) namely, Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST), National Drug Authority (NDA), and Uganda National Health Research Organization (UNHRO) will be included in the study as key informants. The REC Chairpersons, REC members, and researchers were the primary participants for the study. The NRAs and REC administrators are the secondary participants in the study. The list of accredited RECs by UNCST by March 2023 will be generated. In addition, the researchers who conducted research between March 2020 and March 2023 during the COVID-19 and Ebola PHEs will be included in the study. The membership rosters of the RECs that are indicated in table 1 under section 3.3 will be generated for inclusion in the study. The unit of analysis for the study is the research regulation system.

3.5 Sample Size Determination

A total of 73 study participants will be involved in the study. These will include the 29 REC Chairpersons, 29 REC members, and 10 researchers. The study will interview at least 5 participants selected from the relevant National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs) (1) from the Uganda National Health Research Organization (UNHRO), 2 from the National Drug Authority (NDA), and 2 (UNCST).

All the REC administrators from the 29 RECs that will be involved in the study composing of 6-12 participants. Study participants as indicated in Table 2, will be interviewed until the saturation point is reached.

Table 2: Distribution of Participants and Sample Size for the Study

Study Participants	Sample Size	Data Collection Method
REC Chairpersons, REC Members and researchers	68	In-Depth interviews
REC Administrators	4 FGDs	Focus Groups Discussions
Regulators (UNCST, NDA, UNHRO)	5	Key informant interviews

3.6 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

3.6.1 Inclusion Criteria

- i. REC chairpersons who held positions during the research period.
- ii. REC administrators who were appointed and working within the research period.
- iii. Researchers leading clinical trials within the research.
- iv. Participants who consent.

3.6.2 Exclusion Criteria

- i. Participants who do not consent
- ii. Newly accredited RECs

3.7 Sampling Procedures

The research participants from the regulatory agencies and the REC administrators will be purposively selected for the study and interviewed until saturation as key informants. Expert purposive sampling technique will be used for selecting the participants due to their expertise in understanding of the operation of the national regulatory systems. The research regulators have expertise knowledge and experiences related to the research regulation policies and guidelines at both local and international, monitoring and inspection of products, and research for quality assurance. In addition, the regulators have a mandate to understand the unique challenges and experiences faced by the RECs and researchers for possible redress at the national level. The REC administrators have expertise knowledge in the operations of the RECs and a clear understanding of the challenges and experiences of researchers during the processes for registration of the studies. The REC Chairpersons, and REC members for the in-depth interviews will be purposively

selected across the various RECs as per the type of host institution for the views, experiences, and perceptions related to the operation of the REC activities and the coping strategies during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown. All study participants will be interviewed until the saturation point is achieved.

The contact information for the study participants will be extracted from the UNCST accreditation and research registration database and these will be contacted via phone, and emails and invited to participate in the study. The UNCST through the Principal Investigator will introduce the research assistants to the regulatory agencies, researchers, and to the Chairpersons of the accredited RECs that will be involved in the study.

3.8 Data Collection Methods

3.8.1 In-depth Interviews

The in-depth interviews will be conducted among the REC chairpersons, researchers, and REC members. The interviews will be conducted by the researcher and or the research assistants at places with quiet rooms that are convenient to both the researcher and the interviewee. The interviews will be conducted in English and are expected to last for not more than 60 minutes. The in-depth interview guide containing mainly open-ended questions will be used to collect data from the study participants. The tool will address issues related to the research regulation operations, the implementation of the National Research Information Management System (NRIMS), and the challenges experienced during the PHEs. Relatedly, coping strategies that enabled the RECs to function during the pandemic will be described. The detailed information from the participant's thoughts, insights, and experiences will provide data that will be analyzed to achieve the study objectives.

3.8.2 Key Informant Interviews

The key informant interviews will be conducted with the representatives of the national regulators from agencies such as the Uganda National Health Research Organization (UNHRO), the National Drug Authority (NDA), and the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST). The interviews will be conducted by the researcher and or the research assistants at the respective agencies' offices. The interviews will be conducted in English and are expected to last for not more than 60 minutes. The key informant interview guide containing open-ended questions will be used. The issues that will be addressed by the tool will include, the description of how the existing national policies and guidelines were utilized and supported the regulation of research during the pandemic. The coping strategies by the regulatory agencies in supporting the RECs and researchers will also be described. The expert information shared

through the interviews with the regulators will be generated into themes that will inform the study's goals and objectives.

3.8.3 Focus Group Discussions

The FGDs will be conducted with the 29 REC administrators from the 29 accredited RECs that will be included in the study. A workshop model will be adopted for the collection of data from REC administrators. The participants will be interviewed virtually through videoconferencing. The discussions will be handled by at least two research assistants, one will moderate the discussions while the second observe group dynamics, body language, and social interactions. The interviews will be conducted in English and are expected to last between 45-60 minutes.

A total of 4 focus group discussions will be held, each consisting of at least 6-12 REC administrators. The criteria for inclusion in the FGDs will be based on the type of REC host institution and the type of REC reviews. The 4 FGDs include; 1 FGD from hospital-based RECs, 1 FGD from education institution RECs, 1 FGD from RECs that majorly review social sciences and humanities, and the last from RECs that review majorly Medical and health sciences research protocols.

The focus group discussion guide containing open-ended questions will be used. The issues that will be addressed by the tool will include, research regulation operations, the implementation of the National Research Information Management System (NRIMS), and the challenges experienced during the PHEs. The rich data and new ideas generated will emerge with the in-depth interview data before deriving logical conclusions in achieving the specific objectives of the study.

3.9 Data Collection Procedures

The researcher and or the research assistants shall recruit the participants and set appointments for when the interviews shall be conducted. This will focus on the convenience of the participants. The interview shall be administered in English and recorded for purposes of enabling the participants to express themselves but also allowing the moderator to record. Permission will be sought from participants to have proceedings of each interview audio recorded to ensure that all the data is captured accurately. Recordings will be transcribed verbatim, and transcripts will be stored in password-protected computers in preparation for analysis. The interviews will be facilitated by two research assistants with a minimum of a bachelor's degree in a social science-related discipline, in possession of a valid certificate in Human Subject Protection (HSP) course, and have experience in conducting research interviews.

3.10 Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed using the thematic analysis approach outlined by Braun and Clarke (Braun & Clarke, 2008; Vaismoradi, Turunen & Bondas, 2013). This analysis approach was chosen because it is suitable for studying people's perspectives, opinions, and experiences. First, the transcripts will be read and cross-checked against the recordings, with any errors corrected. Data analysis will start by reading all the transcripts repeatedly to gain familiarity with the data. Data will then be read word by word, and phrases or sentences will be highlighted and given shorthand labels called codes. Similar codes will be aggregated to form clusters, and in the process, some codes will be merged while others are discarded. Codes will then be grouped to create themes. Finally, themes that have been developed will be reviewed, defined, and named to provide a clear understanding of the data. The results of the study will be presented using themes with illustrative quotes from the data. To ensure rigor during data analysis, two analysts will independently code the data. Discrepancies in definitions of the codes will be resolved by consensus and by referring to the transcripts.

3.11 Quality Control Measures

All research assistants will be trained on the protocol, study tools, and interviewing skills before the commencement of any study activity. The principal investigator will supervise study activities and meet the research team bi-weekly to minimize errors and manage emerging issues. Before using the interview guides in the actual study, a pilot study will be carried out first to ensure that the tools that will be used in the study are valid and reliable. 1 FGD, 5 in-depth and 2 key informant interviews will be carried out during the pilot study. The pilot will be carried out among the regulators, researchers, and REC members of Bugema University, Uganda Christian University, Kabale University, and Lira University RECs that will not be participating in the study.

Data obtained through field note-taking will be compared with the actual data collected using audio recording to make sure that there is no missing information. Backing of the data will be done regularly and stored on the UNCST data server to protect it against hazards. Finally, for the entire study process, any deviations from the approved proposal will be noted and reported to the REC and UNCST to promote transparency in the study process.

3.12 Ethical Considerations

The UNCST, NARC, and the research team shall ensure that the study is conducted ethically, and in compliance with the national and international guidelines for research involving Humans as Research

Participants (UNCST, 2014). According to Kathryn (2012), “*Researchers have an ethical obligation to minimize the risks that research may pose to participants*” (pg. 151). The purpose of the ethical considerations is to ensure that the rights and welfare of human research participants are protected during research.

Informed consent will be obtained from all study participants before being enrolled in the study. Only the approved; study protocol, informed consent forms, and study tools will be used when conducting the study. Personal identifiable information provided by participants will be kept confidential and measures to protect their privacy will be always ensured while conducting study activities. The participants will be compensated 50,000 shillings for their time, effort, and inconveniences while participating in the study activities. Participation in the study will be voluntary, and participants will be free to withdraw from the study at any time without being penalized. All study participants will get feedback on the progress and the findings of the study.

Ethical and scientific approval to conduct the study will be obtained from the National HIV/AIDS Research Committee and final clearance sought from the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) for registration and approval. The administrative clearances will be sought from UNCST, NDA, and UNHRO before the commencement of any study activity.

3.13 Data Sharing Plan

Data available from the study will be managed and stored by the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST). Both the UNCST and EDCTP will have ownership of the data and as such have full access to de-identified data. EDCTP has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the study results and materials and documents received from the UNCST such as publications in paper or electronic form) for policy, information, communication, dissemination, and publicity purposes during and after the closure of the study. This is guided by the data agreement signed by all consortium partners. All data will be de-identified before sharing and dissemination to all partners. All the data will be destroyed five years after the study is completed. The findings of the study will be shared at a stakeholder meeting involving the RECs, IACUCs, and researchers.

3.14 Community Engagement Plan

In the development of the proposal the Forum for Research Ethics Chairpersons (FRECU) as well as a pool of researchers were consulted. Development of the proposal included members from the FRECU. The community will be engaged during the implementation of the study activities through the various

communication forums i.e emails, WhatsApp groups of stakeholders and workshops. We expect the findings from this study will help the NRAs and RECs in streamlining some of its processes to address gaps during public health emergencies. The findings will be disseminated through reports and presented to the different stakeholders at both local and international conferences and workshops. We will also prepare and submit the findings for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

3.15 COVID-19 Mitigation plan

In conducting this study, the research team will put the following measures in place to protect the research team and the study participants from contracting COVID-19. Both the research team and the research participants will have to wear masks properly during research activities. No study participant will be interviewed without wearing a face mask properly. The research assistants will be provided with masks and will have extra masks to offer to any willing participant that may not have a mask. The research team will ensure adequate ventilation and avoid close contact with the study participants during the study activities. Hand hygiene will be emphasized by hand washing with soap and water or use of an alcohol-based sanitizer. The research team will have hand sanitizer that will be used during the study activities for hand sanitization before and after writing on the study forms.

3.16 Limitations

The interviews will take a lot of time due to the sensitivity of dealing with respondents' emotions about what happened during the COVID-19 pandemic and restrictions. The recall bias may arise as a result of trying to remember the various experiences and operations of the RECs since March 2020. The limitations will be minimized by a careful selection of the research questions, choosing an appropriate data collection method, and ensuring that the strategies to maintain rigor in the conduct and reporting of the study findings are followed. The researcher will recruit trained research assistants who know how to create a good rapport with participants before the interview and put emphasis on maintaining the privacy and confidentiality of the research participants.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: In-Depth Interview Guide for the Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda- REC Chairpersons, REC Members and Researchers

Introduction

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organisation, Jimmy University and University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance. We expect that completing this tool will not take more than 60 minutes. In case you have further inquiries about this exercise, kindly let us know by telephone on : 0772620279/ 0702620279.

A. Experience of the participants:

1. In your opinion, how did the COVID-19 research guidelines support the streamlining of REC operations or conduct of research during the pandemic? How did the policies support the operations or affect the operations? How did the researchers adhere or comply with the research regulations?
2. As a member of the REC/Researcher, what REC Operations were implemented during the pandemic?
3. What are some of the challenges experienced during implementation of the operations?
4. As a member of the REC/researcher, how did you cope with REC operations during the pandemic? What coping strategies are implemented by the REC?
5. Do you think that COVID-19 guidelines had the information in the conduct and regulation of research during a pandemic? (Probe for how).
6. From your experience of the application of the National Research Registration Information Management System (NRIMS), share some of the challenges that you have encountered or observed?
7. How can the above- mentioned challenges be mitigated to ensure a successful usability of the NRIMS?
8. What do you think should be done by the regulatory agencies and RECs to improve the research online application?
9. What opportunities for the regulatory agencies and the RECs do you think COVID-19 pandemic brought on board?

10. What would you like to see change in the regulatory agencies and REC operations after the COVID-19 pandemic?

11. Are there any other important issues that you would like to share that would help to enhance the regular REC operations during public health emergencies?

We have now come to the end of the interview.

Thank you very much for taking time to respond to these questions and your participation in this exercise.

Appendix II: Informant Guide for the Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda- Key Informant Interviews (Regulators)

Introduction

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organisation, Jimmy University and University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance.

A. Experience of the Regulators:

1. In your opinion, how did the national guidelines for conduct of research during COVID–19 help you in supporting REC activities during the pandemic?
2. As regulator, what regulatory activities were conducted during the pandemic? What are some of the regulatory challenges experienced?
3. How were the REC activities conducted within the Institution during the pandemic?
4. How did the UNCST support the REC to use the National Research Registration Information Management System (NRIMS)?
5. Share your experience on the use of the NRIMS system during the pandemic.
6. What do you think should be done by the National Regulatory Agencies to improve the research online application?
7. Do you think COVID-19 had an effect on the research regulatory system in Uganda? Please give more detail.
8. What opportunities do you think COVID-19 pandemic brought on board? What strategies could be used to strengthen and sustain the opportunities?
9. Are there any other important issues that you would like to share that would help to enhance the research regulation in Uganda? What would you like to see change in the REC operations after the pandemic?

We have now come to the end of the interview. Thank you very much for taking time to respond to these questions and your participation in this exercise.

Appendix III: Focus Group Discussion Guide for the Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda-(REC Administrators)

Introduction

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organization, Jimmy University, and the University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance.

A. Experience of the REC Administrator:

1. As a REC administrator, what REC Operations were implemented during the pandemic?
2. What are some of the challenges experienced during implementation of the operations?
3. How did the policies uffect the REC operations during COVID -19? s during ?
4. How did the UNCST support the REC to use the National Research Registration Information Management System (NRIMS)?
5. Share your experience on the use of the NRIMS system during the pandemic.
6. What do you think should be done by the National Regulatory Authorities to improve the research online application?
7. What opportunities for the REC do you think the COVID-19 pandemic brought on board?
8. As a REC administrator, how did you cope with REC operations during the pandemic? What coping strategies are implemented by the REC?
9. What would you like to see change in the REC operations after the COVID-19 pandemic?
10. Are there any other important issues that you would like to share that would help to enhance the regular REC operations during public health emergencies?

We have now come to the end of the interview.

Thank you very much for taking the time to respond to these questions and for your participation in this exercise.

Appendix IV: Informed Consent Form for the Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda- REC Chairperson, REC Members and Researchers

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organization, Jimmy University, and the University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance.

PURPOSE

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information. The study will document how RECs operated amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The investigators want to also identify the challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic to strengthen and develop a comprehensive governance framework in Uganda.

WHAT THE PARTICIPANT WOULD BE ASKED TO DO

You have been chosen to participate in this study because you are one of the REC members or a researcher. The rationale for your inclusion in the interview is for you to provide more insight into how the research regulation and REC operations were affected by COVID-19 and what opportunities or lessons were learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic.

DURATION

The interview will last for 60 minutes. You may stop participating in the interview at any time if you wish without losing any of your rights to the benefits that could accrue from the study.

RISKS OF PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY

The study does not pose any threat of risks and discomforts that a participant might experience while in the study and the investigator will ensure your safety. Some questions may also be sensitive to participants. However, you have a right not to participate in the study should you find the questions very uncomfortable to answer. As a participant, you are allowed to ask any questions that may be unclear to you.

HOW MANY PARTICIPANTS WILL TAKE PART IN THIS STUDY?

The study will involve REC Chairpersons, REC members, REC administrators, researchers, and national regulators (National Drug Authority, UNHRO, and UNCST). It will explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance. For this interview, approximately 30 REC Chairperson/REC Members/10 researchers will participate in the study.

BENEFITS

There are no direct benefits or costs related to the study. You do not have to take part in the research if you do not wish to do so. We hope that this research will document challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned in relation to the Regulation and REC operations during the COVID-19 pandemic. You will get feedback on the findings and progress of the study and any new information that may affect your participation.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The investigators will use the information collected from you for the purposes of the study. The responses will be recorded and transcribed. The data from this transcription will be coded, anonymized, and analyzed. Anonymized data will be stored in a password secured place and only accessible to the researchers and for the purpose of the research project. The data or records can be accessed by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST). . Anonymized data will be kept at the UNCST premises. The protection of privacy and confidentiality of the study participants will be governed by the Uganda Data Protection and Privacy Act (2019). You will be asked to provide at least one telephone contact in case the investigators need to follow up with you for clarification purposes only.

VOLUNTARINESS

Participation in this study is voluntary. Refusal to participate will not result in a penalty or loss of benefit or entitlement of any kind. You can withdraw or terminate your participation in the study any time or even not respond to any question that makes you uncomfortable.

COMPENSATION

The only cost to you for being in the study is your time. There is no payment for being in the study. However, you will be compensated 50,000/= for your time, effort, and inconveniences for participating in the study.

FEEDBACK ON THE FINDINGS

As a study participant, you will get feedback on the progress and the findings of the study through a stakeholders' workshops that will be organized by the UNCST.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

This research has been reviewed and approved by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology.

CONTACTS AND QUESTIONS

If you have concerns regarding related to the study should be addressed to the Ms. Hellen Opolot, on telephone number: 0772620279/0702620279, while those related to rights and welfare should be addressed to Dr. Joseph Ochieng, the REC Chairperson, National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee, on telephone number: 0772426681.

STATEMENT OF PARTICIPANT CONSENT

I.....have been asked to participate in a research study named: **The Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda**. The Principal Investigator or her representative has explained the study to me, the information was read to me, and I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. All questions were answered in the way that I understand. If I have other questions about this research, I can ask the principal investigator on 0772620279/ 0702620279. I understand that my agreement to participate is voluntary and that I can decline to participate. Am signing my name below to indicate my consent to participate in this study. I will be given a copy of the signed consent form.

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Thank you very much for taking the time to read this document. Please complete the section below to confirm your consent to participate in this study.

I agree to participate in the interviews. Yes.....No.....

I agree with audio recording and taking notes during the interviews. Yes.....No.....

Name of participant	Date
Signature of participant	Date.....
Name of person obtaining consent	Date
Signature of person obtaining consent	Date

RISKS OF PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY

The study does not pose any threat of risks and discomforts that a participant might experience while in the study and the investigator will ensure your safety. Some questions may also be sensitive to participants. However, you have a right not to participate in the study should you find the questions very uncomfortable to answer. As a participant, you are allowed to ask any questions that may be unclear to you.

HOW MANY PARTICIPANTS WILL TAKE PART IN THIS STUDY?

The study will involve REC Chairpersons, REC members, REC administrators, researchers, and regulatory agencies (National Drug Authority, UNHRO, and UNCSST). It will explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance. For this particular interview for the key informants, only 5 regulators will participate in the study.

BENEFITS

There are no direct benefits or costs related to the study. You do not have to take part in the research if you do not wish to do so. We hope that this research will document challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned about research regulation and REC operations during the COVID-19 pandemic. You will get feedback on the findings and progress of the study and any new information that may affect your participation.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The investigators will use the information collected from you for the purposes of the study. The responses will be recorded and transcribed. The data from this transcription will be coded, anonymized, and analyzed. Anonymized data will be stored in a password-secured place and only accessible to the researchers and for the research project. The data or records can be accessed by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCSST). Anonymized data will be kept at the UNCSST premises. The protection of privacy and confidentiality of the study participants will be governed by the Uganda Data Protection and Privacy Act (2019). You will be asked to provide at least one telephone contact in case the investigators need to follow up with you for clarification purposes only.

VOLUNTARINESS

Participation in this study is voluntary. Refusal to participate will not result in a penalty or loss of benefit or entitlement of any kind. You can withdraw or terminate your participation in the study any time or even not respond to any question that makes you uncomfortable.

Appendix V: Informed Consent form for the effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda- Key Informant Interviews (Regulators).

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organization, Jimmy University, and the University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance.

PURPOSE

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information. The study will document how research regulation systems and RECs operated amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The investigators want to also identify the challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic to strengthen and develop a comprehensive governance framework in Uganda.

WHAT THE PARTICIPANT WOULD BE ASKED TO DO

You have been chosen to participate in this study because you are one of the research regulators. The rationale for your inclusion in the interview is for you to provide more insight into how the research regulation agencies and RECs operations were affected by COVID-19 and what opportunities or lessons were learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic.

DURATION

The interview will last for 60 minutes. You may stop participating in the interview at any time if you wish without losing any of your rights to the benefits that could accrue from the study.

COMPENSATION

The only cost to you for being in the study is your time. There is no payment for being in the study. However, you will be compensated 50,000/= for your time, effort, and inconveniences for participating in the study.

FEEDBACK ON THE FINDINGS

As a study participant, you will get feedback on the progress and the findings of the study through stakeholders’ workshops that will be organized by the UNCST.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

This research has been reviewed and approved by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee (NARC) and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology.

CONTACTS AND QUESTIONS

If you have concerns regarding related to the study should be addressed to the Ms. Hellen Opolot, on telephone number: 0772620279/0702620279, while those related to rights and welfare should be addressed to Dr. Joseph Ochieng, the REC Chairperson, National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee, on telephone number: 0772426681.

STATEMENT OF PARTICIPANT CONSENT

I..... have been asked to participate in a research study named: **The Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda**. The Principal Investigator or her representative has explained the study to me, the information was read to me, and I have been given the opportunity to ask questions. All questions were answered in the way that I understand. If I have other questions about this research, I can ask the principal investigator on 0772620279/ 0702620279. I understand that my agreement to participate is voluntary and that I can decline to participate. Am signing my name below to indicate my consent to participate in this study. I will be given a copy of the signed consent form.

Thank you very much for taking the time to read this document. Please complete the section below to confirm your consent to participate in this study.

I agree to participate in the interviews. **Yes.....No.....**

I agree with audio recording and taking notes during the interviews. **Yes.....No.....**

Name of participant	Date
Signature of participant	Date.....
Name of person obtaining consent	Date
Signature of person obtaining consent	Date

Appendix VI: Focus Group Discussion-Informed Consent Form for the REC Administrators

The Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST) in collaboration with the National Drug Authority, the Uganda National Health Research Organization, Jimmy University, and the University of Oslo is implementing a project entitled: “Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa (ACCESS2 AFRICA)”, funded by the European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP).

One of the objectives of ACCESS2 AFRICA is to strengthen linkages between regulatory authorities and ethics review committees. In this regard, the UNCST would like to conduct a study that seeks to explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance.

PURPOSE

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information. The study will document how research regulation and RECs operated amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The investigators want to also identify the challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic to strengthen and develop a comprehensive governance framework in Uganda.

WHAT THE PARTICIPANT WOULD BE ASKED TO DO

You have been chosen to participate in this study because you are one of the REC administrators. The rationale for your inclusion in the interview is for you to provide more insight into how research regulation and REC operations were affected by COVID-19 and what opportunities or lessons were learned by the regulators and the RECs during the COVID-19 pandemic. You will be required to attend the meeting with other REC administrators in groups of 6-8 participants. The facilitator will introduce the agenda, the procedures, and the rules for the meeting. The meeting will start with self-introductions, then the discussions will follow. The meeting will be held online, and the discussions will be audio-recorded.

DURATION

The interview will last for 60 minutes. You may stop participating in the interview at any time if you wish without losing any of your rights to the benefits that could accrue from the study.

RISKS OF PARTICIPATING IN THE STUDY

The study does not pose any threat of risks and discomforts that a participant might experience while in the study and the investigator will ensure your safety. Some questions may also be sensitive to participants. However, you have a right not to participate in the study should you find the questions very uncomfortable to answer. As a participant, you are allowed to ask any questions that may be unclear to you.

HOW MANY PARTICIPANTS WILL TAKE PART IN THIS STUDY?

The study will involve REC Chairpersons, REC members, REC administrators, and regulatory agencies (National Drug Authority, UNHRO and UNCST). It will explore the effect of public health emergencies on the research regulatory system in Uganda, over the last three (03) years so that it can strengthen the research regulatory system preparedness and governance. For this interview, approximately 32 REC administrators will participate in the study.

BENEFITS

There are no direct benefits or costs related to the study. You do not have to take part in the research if you do not wish to do so. We hope that this research will document challenges, opportunities, and lessons learned about the Regulation and REC operations during the COVID-19 pandemic. You will get feedback on the findings and progress of the study and any new information that may affect your participation.

CONFIDENTIALITY

The investigators will use the information collected from you for the study. The responses will be recorded and transcribed. The data from this transcription will be coded, anonymized, and analyzed. Anonymized data will be stored in a password-secured place and only accessible to the researchers and for the research project. The data or records can be accessed by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee and Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST). Anonymized data will be kept at the UNCST premises. The protection of privacy and confidentiality of the study participants will be governed by the Uganda Data Protection and Privacy Act (2019). You will be asked to provide at least one telephone contact in case the investigators need to follow up with you for clarification purposes only.

VOLUNTARINESS

Participation in this study is voluntary. Refusal to participate will not result in a penalty or loss of benefit or entitlement of any kind. You can withdraw or terminate your participation in the study at any time or even not respond to any question that makes you uncomfortable.

COMPENSATION

The only cost to you for being in the study is your time. There is no payment for being in the study. However, you will be compensated 50,000/= for your time, effort, and inconveniences in participating in the study. In addition, a snack and a drink will be provided to all study participants for the focus group discussions.

FEEDBACK ON THE FINDINGS

As a study participant, you will get feedback on the progress and the findings of the study through stakeholders' workshops that will be organized by the UNCST.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

This research has been reviewed and approved by the National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee and the Uganda National Council for Science and Technology.

CONTACTS AND QUESTIONS

If you have concerns related to the study should be addressed to Ms. Hellen Opolot, on telephone number: 0772620279/0702620279, while those related to rights and welfare should be addressed to Dr. Joseph Ochieng, the REC Chairperson, National HIV/AIDS Research Ethics Committee, on telephone number: 0772426681.

STATEMENT OF PARTICIPANT CONSENT

I..... have been asked to participate in a research study named: **The Effect of Public Health Emergencies on the Research Regulatory Systems: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 in Uganda**. The Principal Investigator or her representative has explained the study to me, the information was read to me, and I have been allowed to ask questions. All questions were answered in the way that I understand. If I have other questions about this research, I can ask the principal investigator on 0772620279/ 0702620279. I understand that my agreement to participate is voluntary and that I can decline

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to participate. Am signing my name below to indicate my consent to participate in this study. I will be given a copy of the signed consent form.

Thank you very much for taking the time to read this document. Please complete the section below to confirm your consent to participate in this study.

I agree to participate in the interviews. **Yes**.....**No**.....

I agree with audio recording. **Yes**.....**No**.....

Name of participant	Date
Signature of participant	Date.....
Name of person obtaining consent	Date
Signature of person obtaining consent	Date

Appendix VII: Study Work Plan

	Aug 2023	Sept 2023	Oct 2023	Nov 2023	Dec 2023	Jan 2024	Feb 2024	Sept 2024	Sept 2024	Feb 2025	June 2026
Protocol and tool development	█										
Approval of study				█							
Data Collection						█					
Data Analysis									█		
Dissemination											█

Appendix VIII: Study Budget

No	Item	Description	Unit price	Quantity	Total
1.	Protocol development	Protocol development meetings	100,000	10x 3 meetings	3,000,000
2.	Peer review-protocol development	Investigators meeting	150,000	3 persons X 3 days	1,350,000
3.	REC review	NARC fees	400\$	1* 3700	1,480,000
4.	UNCST review fees	Fees	300\$	1* 3700	1,110,000
5.	Data Collection and Transcription		1	1	12,750,000
6.	Analysis and Report		1	1	11,400,000
7.	Dissemination	Venue	150,000	60	3,000,000
		Transport	100,000	60	6,000,000
		Writing and publication of manuscript	n/a	n/a	n/a

